

Firmware update in Linux using Linux Vendor Firmware Service, potential risks of blobs substitution.

Smirnov Roman— developer, Rosseti-Digital mail@romansmirnov.org

Annotation.

The article discusses the mechanism for updating the built-in software (firmware) in distributions of the Linux operating system (OS). It is concluded that there are potential vulnerabilities in this mechanism and a solution is proposed in the form of organizing own service for additional verification of "firmware" as well as public monitoring fwupd service functioning.

Keywords: embedded software, Linux OS, Linux vendor firmware service, fwupd, LVFS, public data verification

Introduction

In 2015, Richard Hughes, one of the developers of Gnome, and also part-time employee of Dell, developed a service for updating the so-called. device firmware for the operating system (hereinafter OS) Linux, which was originally intended for use by Dell [1]

Over time, the Linux Vendor Firmware Service (hereinafter referred to as LVFS) has gained popularity and is currently included in most of the most common Linux OS distributions - Ubuntu, Debian, RedHat and others built on their basis.

The project does not have public statistics, as of December 1, 2021, the owners of the service declared 40 million firmware downloads (the year before there were 25 million) [2], as of May 31, 2022 - about 52 million downloads [3] i.e. it is actively used all over the world.

The principle of operation of the service is schematically shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. How fwupd and lvfs work

The LVFS Firmware Service provides resources and support to enable OEMs to rapidly update end-user firmware.

The fwupd service running on the client computer periodically downloads a metadata index with information about drivers from the lvfs server, then compares the match with the attributes of devices connected to the computer according to the conditions specified in the metadata and, if necessary, updates (most often via UEFI).

Thus, a targeted download can be organized for certain clients, based on the information (IP address and its correspondence to the geographical area / belonging) transmitted during the connection, modified firmware images (including together with the data in the index)

It is also possible to modify the firmware directly when vendors upload files to the service. The owners of LVFS declare that all files uploaded by manufacturers are checked by ClamAV antivirus and uploaded to VirusTotal for further analysis [4]. However, these services have never dealt specifically with Pre-OS threats and have not specialized in UEFI, i.e. are not authoritative sources in this area.

There is a commercial service Binary FwHunt with private commercial experts on the topic in the composition, which monitors LVFS for the appearance of devices vulnerable to attack firmware (it can also be used for the operational development of the attacks themselves).

Experiment

To analyze the firmware update mechanism, monitoring software was developed (publicly available under the GPLv3 license [5]), a service that downloads the index daily and calculated the difference with the previous data received, the processing results were stored in the

database, the scheme of which is shown in Fig. 2

Fig 2. Database schema used to monitor the LVFS repository

Basic entities -

1. Components - Device Drivers

	123 uhistoryid	ABC componentid	ABC componentna	ABC summary	ABC url
55	1	com.eposaudio.USBEDCC01.fir	USB ED CC 01	Adapter with call control, USB to ED	https://www.eposaudio.com/er
56	1	com.fingerprints.lenfy.firmwar	FPC Disum	Firmware for FPC Disum Fingerprint Reader device	https://www.fingerprints.com/
57	1	com.formlife.studio.firmware	Studio Sys UPD	Firmware for the Studio device	http://www.pegatroncorp.com/
58	1	com.fujitsu.D3543-A1.Firmwar	D3543-A1	UEFI Firmware for D3543-A1 System Board	https://www.Fujitsu.com/
59	1	com.fujitsu.D3543-A1.uefi.firm	D3543-A1	UEFI Firmware for D3543-A1 System Board	https://www.Fujitsu.com/
60	1	com.fujitsu.D3543-A2.uefi.firm	D3543-A2	UEFI Firmware for D3543-A2 System Board	https://www.Fujitsu.com/
61	1	com.fujitsu.D3544-A1.Firmwar	D3544-A1	UEFI Firmware for D3544-A1 System Board	https://www.Fujitsu.com/
62	1	com.fuiitsu.D3544-A1.uefi.firm	D3544-A1	UEFI Firmware for D3544-A1 Svstem Board	httos://www.Fuiitsu.com/

Table 1. Example data - Components

1. ComponentsReleases - Driver releases, sample data

123 id	123	123	ABC n	ABC	releasestimestamp	ABC	ABC releaselocation	ABC releasedescription
79	1	57	8765	108041	2021-06-30 00:00:00.000	mediur	https://fwupd.org/downloads/b7eb1c37489777694	This update fixes a compatibility issue which was ob
80	1	58	22352	619125	2023-03-03 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/4d52fb2fedb014963	Dell PC SN810 NVMe SSD Firmware Update which inc
81	1	58	12480	615200	2022-03-21 10:29:26.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/3377039b21e8c8cfa	Dell PC SN810 NVMe SSD Firmware Update which inc
82	1	59	16873	340000	2022-11-18 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/9d59a15b1d863020	This stable release fixes the following:FW releaseFW f
83	1	59	11963	340000	2022-02-15 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/dbf3a0600e2983727	This stable release fixes the following:This FW release
84	1	60	18087	346000	2023-01-15 00:00:00.000	critical	https://fwupd.org/downloads/01752390fca47ff351	This stable release fixes the following:FW releaseGC c
85	1	61	16057	245000	2022-10-12 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/f0b5e58dceafab155	This stable release fixes the following:FW releaseRem
86	1	62	19319	112001	2023-03-01 00:00:00.000	mediur	https://fwupd.org/downloads/9e3adb9b7a34ecd6	Fix LPM handling issue, LUT overwritten issue and au
87	1	62	14816	112001	2022-08-05 00:00:00.000	low	https://fwupd.org/downloads/8bed0ad541c3a6d0	FW modification for removing redundant code of thi
88	1	62	12233	112001	2022-02-18 00:00:00.000	low	https://fwupd.org/downloads/e922aac31d935e32e	This FW update includes Chromebook and Ubuntu P
89	1	63	19261	922123	2023-02-10 00:00:00.000	mediur	https://fwupd.org/downloads/1672410cd5ba80c0c	This stable release fixes the following:FW releaseFixe
90	1	63	16671	922100	2022-11-09 00:00:00.000	mediur	https://fwupd.org/downloads/4c2aa6c6ce36a44ct	This stable release fixes the following:FW releaseFixe
91	1	64	33505	510051	2021-03-18 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/d3db99ae153e9cf9f	This is the firmware to update for BC901 for new versio
92	1	65	17431	739141	2022-12-21 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/02bba560c24bdfb4f	Dell PC SN740 NVMe SSD Firmware for dellSupports:
93	1	65	11317	731030	2021-12-22 12:06:51.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/35d850d8c67efdact	WD PC SN740 NVMe SSD FW update for Dell (731030
94	1	66	27470	413000	2023-03-06 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/77ab61f4af6b60128	This firmware provides the following:Fixed compatib
95	1	67	17290	240000	2022-12-15 00:00:00.000	high	https://fwupd.org/downloads/83e97e64e3e5a2cc3	This stable release fixes the following:FW releaseDLL

2.

Table 2. Example data - ComponensReleases

Other tables - ReleaseFiles - hashes of release files, UnloadHistory - history of data downloads. ComponentsChangeHistory and ReleaseChangeHistory contain the results of comparing indices by component and by release.

The results of monitoring the LVFS index from 08/13/2023 to 08/22/2023:

Top 15 Vendors by the number of drivers available in the repository

	ABC developername	123 c
1	Lenovo	650
2	Dell	437
3	HP	39
4	Star Labs	20
5	EPOS	20
6	Fujitsu	16
7	Synaptics	12
8	Nordic	11
9	Wacom	8
10	8BitDo	8
11	Adlink	6
12	Logitech	5
13	System76	4
14	NovaCustom	3
15	Corsair	3

Table 3 – Vendors

Features noticed during the monitoring period:

1. Permanent removal of components:

id	123	123	ABC componentid	ABC operationtype	ABC info
1	2	1	com.dell.uefi6e7d6855.firmware	new	20230813T
2	2	1	com.lenovo.ThinkPadN1VRG.corporate.firmware	new	20230813T
3	2	1	com.lenovo.ThinkPadN25RG.Consumer.firmware	new	20230813T
4	2	1	com.lenovo.ThinkPadN25RG.firmware	new	20230813T
5	2	1	com.lenovo.ThinkPadN38HT.firmware	new	20230813T
6	4	3	com.adlinktech.COM-HPC.firmware	new	20230815T
7	5	4	com.adlinktech.COM-HPC-ALT-BIOS.firmware	new	20230816T
8	5	4	com.adlinktech.COM-HPC.firmware	removed	20230816T
9	6	5	com.adlinktech.COM-HPC-ALT-CC.firmware	new	20230817T
10	6	5	com.dell.uefi4d7bdc4_Precision5530.firmware	new	20230817T
11	6	5	com.adlinktech.COM-HPC-ALT-BIOS.firmware	removed	20230817T

Table 4. Removed components

For example, on August 15, 2023, the firmware for the AdLinkTech COM-HPC computing module was downloaded, which was permanently deleted the next day.

3. Deleting release files

23	123	ABC componentname	releasetimestamp	ABC rel	ABC releasedescription	ABC operator
8	7	Inspiron 15 3520, Inspiron 15 3520, Vostr	2023-06-28 00:00:00.000	69632	Fixes and Enhancements=====	new
8	7	Inspiron 15 3520, Vostro 3520, Vostro 34	2023-06-28 00:00:00.000	69632	Fixes and Enhancements=====	new
8	7	Inspiron 15 3520, Inspiron 15 3520, Vostr	2023-06-28 00:00:00.000	69632	Fixes and Enhancements=====	new
8	7	ThinkPad L14 L15 Gen3 AMD	2023-04-21 00:00:00.000	0.1.18	Lenovo ThinkPad L14 L15 Gen3 AMD Embedded con	removed
8	7	Inspiron 3530, Vostro 3530, Vostro 3430	2023-01-19 00:00:00.000	65792	Fixes and Enhancements :Supports 13th Generation I	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3511, Vostro 15 3510	2022-12-20 00:00:00.000	70656	Fixes and Enhancements :=====	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3511, Vostro 15 3510	2022-12-20 00:00:00.000	70656	Fixes and Enhancements :=====	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3511, Vostro 15 3510	2022-12-19 00:00:00.000	70656	Fixes and Enhancements :=====	removed
8	7	Inspiron/Vostro 3X8X	2022-12-19 00:00:00.000	71169	Fixes and Enhancements :-----Firmware	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3511, Vostro 15 3510	2022-12-19 00:00:00.000	70656	Fixes and Enhancements :=====	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3520, Inspiron 15 3520, Vostr	2022-12-15 00:00:00.000	68096	Fixes and Enhancements :-----Firmware	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3520, Inspiron 15 3520, Vostr	2022-12-15 00:00:00.000	68096	Fixes and Enhancements :-----Firmware	removed
8	7	Inspiron 15 3520, Vostro 3520, Vostro 34	2022-12-14 00:00:00.000	68096	Fixes and Enhancements :-----Firmware	removed
8	7	Inspiron/Vostro 3X8X	2022-11-14 00:00:00.000	70656	Fixes and Enhancements :-----Firmware	removed
8	7	Inspiron 5493,Inspiron 5593,Inspiron 349	2022-09-12 00:00:00.000	71680	Fixes and Enhancements :Firmware updates to addre	removed
11	10	Precision 7670, Precision 7770	2023-07-26 00:00:00.000	69121	This stable release fixes the following issues:Fixed the	new
11	10	ThinkPad X1 Nano Gen 2	2023-07-26 00:00:00.000	0.1.21	BIOS and ECFW firmware Update For Reference code	new
11	10	Precision 7680, Precision 7780	2023-07-10 00:00:00.000	66817	This stable release fixes the following issues:This rele	new
11	10	ThinkPad X1 Nano Gen 2	2023-07-08 00:00:00.000	0.1.18	BIOS and ECFW regular update for reference code.	new
11	10	Latitude 3410, Latitude 3510	2023-07-06 00:00:00.000	71936	This stable release fixes the following issues:This rele	new
11	10	WD22 USB4	2023-05-04 14:18:35.000	38.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	new
11	10	WD19 Thunderbolt	2023-05-04 14:18:35.000	60.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	new
11	10	WD22 USB4	2022-06-08 02:48:05.000	38.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	new
11	10	WD19 Thunderbolt	2022-06-08 02:48:05.000	60.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	new
11	10	Thunderbolt	2023-05-04 14:18:35.000	60.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	removed
11	10	USB4	2023-05-04 14:18:35.000	38.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	removed
11	10	Precision 7680, Precision 7780	2023-04-13 00:00:00.000	66050	This stable release fixes the following issues:This rele	removed
11	10	Precision 7670, Precision 7770	2023-03-14 00:00:00.000	68352	This stable release fixes the following issues:This rele	removed
11	10	ThinkPad X1 Nano Gen 2	2022-12-13 00:00:00.000	0.1.18	New functions or enhancementsUpdated the Diagno	removed
11	10	ThinkPad X1 Nano Gen 2	2022-12-08 00:00:00.000	0.1.15	Lenovo ThinkPad X1 Nano Gen 2 Embedded controll	removed
11	10	Latitude 3410, Latitude 3510	2022-08-15 00:00:00.000	70144	This stable release fixes the following issues:Fixed the	removed
11	10	USB4	2022-06-08 02:48:05.000	38.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	removed
11	10	Thunderbolt	2022-06-08 02:48:05.000	60.00	-Same as previous release, there is no change for this	removed

Table 5. Changes in release files

Release files are deleted on a regular basis and links to old files are not stored in the index. An example is shown in table 5.

Thus, even in a short period of monitoring, cases have already been found that, in addition to a directly vulnerable scheme, indicate the impossibility of restoring the change history in case there are any problems with a certain "update".

Conclusion

The fwupd service successfully performs the functions of updating software and drivers, by its architecture it can be used (already actively used) when operating on critical infrastructure components, subject to the presence of an additional verification level and updating history, preliminary testing of downloaded firmware in artificial environments, etc. n. "sandboxes".

Accordingly, it is possible to develop automated or semi-automated services for pre-checking firmware before using it in a working environment, incl. on critical infrastructure, and in the case of standardization of the approach as a whole, scaling it to update specialized software through a single repository that is independent of distributions. It is also worth noting that the analysis of the operating experience of the LVFS service (hardware configuration, server software, etc.), if necessary, will allow creating an analogue, in the future with the improvement and standardization of the firmware update process including updating to modern approaches for data integrity checking [6] or even blockchain based schemes [7] covering whole process.

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